

PROGRESS OF PHOTODETECTORS BASED ON CHARACTERIZATION METHOD - A REVIEW

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Abstract

This review presents the findings of comprehensive analyses and research efforts focused on establishing a standardized approach for conceptualizing and measuring photodetector parameters. Photodetectors play a crucial role in converting incoming optical radiation into electrical signals in various advanced optoelectronic systems, as well as common everyday devices like smart watches and systems. Different types of photodetectors are discussed to describe their performance, which is determined by the manufacturing technology and internal architecture. Subsequently, the article delves into the metrological aspects of the characterization of photodetectors.

Keywords:

photodetectors, photoconductive detector, photodetector characteristics, MIS structure

1. INTRODUCTION

The performance of optoelectronic techniques is heavily reliant on quality of the photodetectors. This crucial component converts the optical energy into electrical energy and serves as the primary front-end element of an optical receiver. In order to meet the demands of various applications, photodetectors must possess exceptional speed and provide a superior signal-to-noise ratio. As such, they should demonstrate low levels of noise, along with higher levels of quantum efficiency and system response time. The general chronology of photodetectors structure improvement includes intrinsic, extrinsic photoconductors, MIS structured (metal-insulator-semiconductor) photodiodes, Schottky barrier photodiodes and avalanche photodiodes [1, 2]. In this review, we discuss the basic parameters and measuring system of photodetectors.

2. PHOTODETECTOR PARAMETERS

2.1 PHOTOCONDUCTIVE DETECTORS

Semiconductors generate free carriers and increase electrical conductivity. The classification of photoconductive detectors include extrinsic and intrinsic. The intrinsic types of detectors employ the absorption of photons with adequate sources to generate electron, holes combine in a semiconductor, while extrinsic type detector relies on the process of contaminant within the semiconductors to generate free carriers and augment electrical conductivity [3]. Fig.1 shows the structure of photoconductive detector

Fig.1. Structure of photoconductive detector

Responsivity of photodiode

$$R \equiv \frac{I_{\text{photo}}}{P_{\text{inc}}} = \frac{\eta e \tau_r}{h\nu \tau_t}$$

Photoconductive gain

$$G_p \equiv \frac{\tau_r}{\tau_t} = \frac{\tau_r \mu U}{d^2}$$

Fig.2 shows the structure of p-n junction diode. A p-type/n-type junction diode is commonly utilized optical detectors is the p-type /n-type photodiode. The light quantum with energy exceeding the semiconductor energy gap strike neutral zones on either side of depletion region, electrons-holes combine are formed. Subsequently, the charges generated inside the carrier length start the junction barrier diffuse towards the depletion region, where they undergo separation due to an electric field [4].

Fig. 2. Structure of p-n junction diode

Responsivity of Si - silicon photodiode is calculated by

$$R_{\lambda} = \frac{I_p}{P}$$

3. I-V CHARACTERISTICS

When FB - forward bias is given to the circuit and current increased, dark current calculated by:

$$I_D = I_{SAT} \left(e^{\frac{qV_A}{k_B T}} - 1 \right)$$

I-V curve by the amount of photocurrent by

$$I_{TOTAL} = I_{SAT} \left(e^{\frac{qV_A}{k_B T}} - 1 \right) - I_p$$

Fig. 3. shows the structure of Schottky barrier photodiode. A Schottky barrier photodiode is a device that primarily relies on majority carriers and is created at the junction of a metal and a semiconductor. Just like the p-type /n-type junction, MS structure (metal/semiconductor) link forms a source barrier was separates the electron-hole pairs produced by light [5]. However, it is worth noting that Schottky barrier photodiodes also exhibit a relatively high dark current.

Fig. 3. Structure of Schottky barrier photodiode

Fig.4 shows the structure of MIS photodiode. The MIS photodiode is composed insulator that serves to different the metal terminal from the surface of semiconductor. The critical aspect in the photodiode fabricate is ensuring that insulation layer was of an appropriate thickness, which should not be less than approximately 10 nm. If the insulating layer becomes thinner, there is a possibility of electrons tunnelling through the quantum layer [3].

Fig. 4. Structure of MIS photodiode

Fig.5 shows the structure of Avalanche photodiode. An Avalanche photodiode is capable of detecting a feeble optical signal by utilizing the avalanche multiplication of carriers. To ensure that band gap increase the n-type surface, a sufficiently large reverse bias is applied to the device. Photon absorption takes place in the p-type surface [6]. The avalanche photodiode provides a blend of exceptional speed, sensitivity, and quantum efficiency

Fig.5. Structure of Avalanche photodiode

Fig.6 shows the structure of PIN diode. A PIN photodiode is a photodiode that follows a standard design, with intrinsic type region positioned, connecting the p/n surface regions. These regions are typically heavily doped to ensure proper electrical contacts. When a reverse bias is applied, the band gap regions extend throughout the intrinsic surface volume. In this configuration, direct the photons were only absorbance the band gap region, leading to the creation of electron-hole pairs [7]. It may be negligible if there is a significant energy gap.

Fig. 6. Structure of PIN diode

The band gap layer is a combination of photo diodes and photo conductors. Instead of having a space charge region, it has a uni-polar electron neutralizing barrier, allowing the flow of increased holes without obstruction [8]. The introduction of a uni-polar charge carriers helps repress dark current noise while allowing the flow of photocurrent.

Source of the Diode	Using Method	Name of excitation	Measured Wavelength (nm)	Ref
Ti sapphire laser	Time response	LASER pulse	800	9
DFB LASER diode	Heterodyne	Thermal LASER	1300	10
DFB LASER	Pulse spectrum	LASER pulse	1300	10
Nd:YAG	Heterodyne	Thermal LASER	1319	11
DFB LASER	2-tone Optical	Microwave	1550	12
DFB LASER	Photocurrent	Noise signal	1550	13
LED	Optical noise	Spontaneous heat noise	1550	14

Table 1. Photodetector frequency response

The table I is list of characteristic measurement of photodetector frequency response.

4. CONCLUSION

The article examines various metrological aspects concerning the advancement of technology and the utilization of photodetectors. It stems from thorough analyzed and research aim establishing standardized concepts, the measurement techniques for detector parameters. The article provides a comprehensive description of the frequently employed semiconductor detectors, emphasizing their internal structure and its profound influence on their performance and application.

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